

St Bartholomew's Priory

also known as “St Bartholomew the Great”, “The Priory Church of St Bartholomew, West Smithfield”

By Charlotte Gauthier, Royal Holloway, University of London

Entry tags: Monastic Order, Religious Group, Monastery, Medieval Christianity, Monasticism, Christian Traditions, Anglican, Medieval Christianity, Religious Place

St Bartholomew's Priory and Hospital were founded in 1123 by Rahere, sometime courtier (and possibly court jester) of King Henry I. When Henry's only son and heir William Ætheling was killed along with 300 others in the sinking of the White Ship, Rahere appears to have reconsidered his life. He went on pilgrimage to Rome, where he fell ill and was likely taken to the Hospital of St Bartholomew on Tiber Island. In the extremity of his illness, Rahere vowed that if he were to regain his health, he would build a hospital to treat the poor of London. While convalescing, Rahere had a vision in which he was held by a monster over a fathomless black pit. St Bartholomew came to Rahere's rescue, instructing him to build a priory as well as a hospital on the 'smooth field' outside London's city walls – at that time home both to the king's market and the town gallows. Returning to London, Rahere convinced the bishop of London and King Henry to allow him to build a priory and hospital in Smithfield, as the Apostle instructed. The foundation stone was laid on 25 March 1123. The priory grew from 13 canons to over 35 by the end of the Middle Ages, and was at the centre of medieval London life. Its canons preached and taught across London, working to relieve the wants of the poor. The yearly Bartholomew Fair, held in the priory fairground, provided not only an outlet for sales of woollen cloth, but also three days of high revelry and of scholarly disputations in the churchyard. St Bartholomew's Priory was one of the largest and wealthiest monastic foundations in medieval London, occupying a 9-acre site just north of the London city walls. To the splendid Romanesque core (ca. 1123-1140) of the quire was later added a Gothic clerestory (ca. 1220). The nave, (ca. 1180-1220) was Perpendicular Gothic - remains of the first bay can still be seen inside the church. The final bay of the nave with the former south west aisle door was converted into a gatehouse after the Dissolution, and a Tudor gatehouse (ca. 1560s) built on top of it. Around the year 1400, a programme of works was undertaken that resulted in the founder's splendid tomb - still to be seen in the church - and a chantry chapel for Roger Walden (bishop of London and former archbishop of Canterbury) which was torn down probably by the 1560s. The Dissolution of the Monasteries came to St Bartholomew's in 1539. The former Priory was sold to Sir Richard Rich; its nave was torn down and many of the former monastic buildings converted into private houses for influential courtiers. Under Mary I, Dominican friars briefly occupied the site; at her death, the priory church again became the Church of England parish church, as it remains today.

Date Range: 1123 CE - 2023 CE

Region: St Bartholomew's Priory and Hospital

Region tags: Europe, British Isles, England, London

The former extent of St Bartholomew's Priory and Hospital

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Other [specify]: Cruciform

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Burnt, Torn Down

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Gauthier, Charlotte, ed., 900 Years of St Bartholomew the Great: The History, Art and Architecture of London's Oldest Parish Church (London: Ad Ilissum, 2023)

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol1>

– Source 1 Description: E A Webb, The Records of St. Bartholomew's Priory and St. Bartholomew the Great, West Smithfield: Volume 1 (Oxford, 1921), British History Online

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol2>

– Source 2 Description: E A Webb, The Records of St. Bartholomew's Priory and St. Bartholomew the Great, West Smithfield: Volume 2 (Oxford, 1921), British History Online <http://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol2> [accessed 8 February 2023].

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 1988

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: St Bartholomew the Great Churchyard Excavation

Notes: Details in London Archaeologist. vol.6, No.2 (Spring 1989), 48

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

–King or emperor

- Religious specialists affiliated with political entity
- Private individual

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

- Yes

Groups:

- Priests
- Men
- Children
- Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

- Yes

Specify

- Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Saint Bartholomew

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- Yes

Specify

- Other [specify]: Vision

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

- Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gauthier, Charlotte, ed., 900 Years of St Bartholomew the Great: The History, Art and Architecture of London's Oldest Parish Church (London: Ad Ilissum, 2023)

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol1>
- Source 1 Description: E A Webb, The Records of St. Bartholomew's Priory and St. Bartholomew the Great, West Smithfield: Volume 1 (Oxford, 1921), British History Online
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol2>
- Source 2 Description: E A Webb, The Records of St. Bartholomew's Priory and St. Bartholomew the Great, West Smithfield: Volume 2 (Oxford, 1921), British History Online <http://www.british-history.ac.uk/st-barts-records/vol2> [accessed 8 February 2023].

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

- Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1988

↳ Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: St Bartholomew the Great Churchyard Excavation

Notes: Details in London Archaeologist. vol.6, No.2 (Spring 1989), 48

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

- Leveling of ground
- Trackway or road-surface
- Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

–Other [specify]: Cruciform

↳ One single feature

– Purposefully placed plants

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Other [specify]: Burnt, Torn Down

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For economic reasons

– For political reasons

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

– Private individual

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Children

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Revealed by other kind of supernatural being(s) [specify]: Saint Bartholomew

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Vision

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick, Glass

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick, Glass

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: It contains the tomb of the priory's founder, Rahere, but is not itself a tomb.

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: On days determined by the religious calendar

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

–All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: 120

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Priest

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:
– Yes

↳ In cemetery:
– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:
– Yes

↳ Domestic context:
Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: It contains the tomb of the priory's founder, Rahere, but is not itself a tomb.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– I don't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Priest

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: On days determined by the religious calendar

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 120
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
 - No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes
- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - No
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
 - No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes
- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - Yes
- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - Yes
- ↳ Function for water management:
 - Yes
- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– I don't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– Yes

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

- ↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:
 - I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: St Bartholomew's Priory, Gauthier, Charlotte, ed.. 900 Years of St Bartholomew the Great: The History, Art and Architecture of London's Oldest Parish Church. Edited by Charlotte Gauthier. London: Ad Ilissum, 2022. <https://www.paulholberton.com/product-page/900-years-of-st-bartholomew-s>.